

An Analysis on Motivational Factors Affecting the Rise of Korean Restaurants in the Province of Cavite

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Abstract: Driven by the surge of Korean cultural influence ("Hallyu"), Korean-themed restaurants are flourishing worldwide. This study investigates the motivational factors behind this phenomenon in Dasmaringas, Cavite, Philippines. Focusing on five key factors: cultural curiosity, drama attractiveness, cultural similarity, relationship factor, and viewing habit, we analyze their correlation with the rise of Korean restaurants from both consumer and entrepreneur perspectives. Utilizing a correlational research design, we employ diverse statistical methods including correlation coefficients, weighted means, frequencies, and percentages to assess the significance of each factor. This comprehensive evaluation aims to identify the most influential motivators, empowering future entrepreneurs with data-driven insights for strategic planning and successful Korean restaurant ventures.

Keywords: Consumer, Entrepreneur, Motivational Factors, Hallyu Wave.

1. INTRODUCTION

Korean Hallyu wave is a term used to describe the love for Korean culture and wanting to experience it for themselves, the cause of this can come from various sources such as: music, food, fashion, or even TV shows/movies. The Korean Hallyu wave had affected the Philippines, which caused the Philippines to give a rise towards Korean culture through restaurants, TV dramas, and other platforms. The Korean Hallyu wave has provided numerous opportunities for the Philippines and has inspired so many new innovations. Several restaurants have adapted modern business models and decoration styles just to stay relevant with the current trends. From its popularity to the ever-growing menu, the researchers have asked themselves; Why should people put up more Korean restaurants? And what is the motivational driving factor that keeps customers inspired to visit Korean restaurants?

According to Lizzie Streit (2021) "Because they are often high in vegetables and cooked without much oil, Korean meals are often lower in calories than Traditional American Meals". With that stated, it is ensured that Korean food is the interest of those people who are trying to eat healthy in the decision of food consumption. Healthy dishes are the current trend in today's time, you will notice in America, they include detailed information about their food such as their Calories that people are consuming or in Korea, they focus their dishes with lots of vegetables such as their signature dish "Kimchi". Since, we have an idea on the marketplace globally, in the Philippines, we have been following different cultures for generations, most specifically from the Spanish era and the American era. It is because of these countries that allowed the Philippines to develop their economic standards. In modern times, the Philippines welcomes Globalization by allowing

cultures from other countries to start a business in their land. You will notice that Korean products are mostly been seen or heard from Filipinos, this is because we were influenced by the Hallyu wave and therefore we have interest in what the Hallyu wave cultural products provided. This trend led to the rise of Korean Restaurants in the Philippines but the researchers specifically aim to understand what motivated the Filipinos to even try their culture for the first time. Entrepreneurs are business makers that aim to provide a well-suited establishment for people to enjoy. Entrepreneurs tend to create businesses based on their interests and trends and due to the Hallyu wave rising, this is a perfect opportunity to make profit out of it. People demand Korean Culture; Entrepreneurs will supply the market's demand and one of the best businesses to start up for this trend are the Korean Restaurants. But, unknown food menu chosen by Filipinos is a double-edged sword, either they like it or not. So, what motivates customers to eat in a Korean Restaurant compared to their own safe decision, to eat in a Filipino Restaurant. That is where the Entrepreneurs pitch in and demonstrate what Filipino's are missing through marketing and responding to their wants or common goal. Entrepreneurs have many reasons to build a Korean restaurant while it is still a trend and Filipino's have many reasons to try these businesses, especially when its new to them.

The researchers aim to identify the motivational factors that led to the rise of Korean restaurants in the Philippines. Why is there an increased demand for Korean Restaurants and if the researchers defined the motivational factors for customers to demand Korean restaurants, can it be used to enhance the chances for success for entrepreneurs building these restaurants compared to other cuisine restaurants. The researchers will formulate an understanding of consumer decisions being influenced by trends such as the hallyu wave. Finally, the researchers intend to identify possible strategies that can be used after identifying the main motivational factor for customers to eat in Korean restaurants for entrepreneurs to take note.

Research Paradigm

Figure 1.1 IPO Model

This Figure shows the IPO Model of the study. The results of the survey will show the evaluation of which motivational factor effectively motivates the rise of Korean Restaurants in Cavite.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to identify the correlation of Korean Drama to the rise of Korean Restaurants in Cavite.

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1.. As a customer which motivational factors signifies the most and least in going to Korean restaurants based on the five motivational factors provided.

- a. Viewing Habit
- b. Drama Attractiveness
- c. Cultural Curiosity
- d. Cultural Similarity
- e. Relationship Factor

1. As an entrepreneur which motivational factor signifies as the most and least in visualizing an ideal Korean restaurant business
 - a. Viewing Habit
 - b. Drama Attractiveness
 - c. Cultural Curiosity
 - d. Cultural Similarity
 - e. Relationship Factor
2. Which factor is most likely the reason in the rise of Korean restaurants in the Philippines.
3. What made the entrepreneur student decide to choose this certain motivational factor.
4. Is there a significant difference among the ratings of customer point of view compared to entrepreneur point of view.
5. Formulate a strategy on how the most significant motivational factor can be used to build an ideal Korean restaurant.

Statement of Hypothesis

Ho: None of the factors were proven to be effective in terms of customer motivation to eat in Korean Restaurants.

Ho: There is no significant difference between the five factors which describes the results as either all factors have been considered or none of them were effective.

Ho: None of the factors had significance to the rise of Korean restaurants in the Philippines.

Ho: There was no reason why the entrepreneur students chose this certain motivational factor because none of them motivated the entrepreneur student

Ho: There was no strategy implemented for the benefit of future entrepreneurs to build their own business.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Demographic Factors when Visiting Restaurants

According to Khan & Aditi (2020) from Global Journal of Management in their research about “Factors Affecting Eating out in Restaurants: A Study on Customer of Dharka City” It has been stated that it was vital to understand the demographics of this study focuses on the Gender and Age of the respondents. They were also inquiring about what are the possible factors that could allow a customer to decide to eat outside of their homes and it was stated that it varies based on the following: Purpose of visit, Frequency of visit, Average Monthly Spending for eating out and Attributes affecting customer choices of restaurants. The result for demographic profile shows that there is no significant difference between males and females other than their attributes affecting customers’ choices. In terms of Age, they correlate it to the purpose of visit, and it represented that there was a meaningful relationship to ages 26-40+ to visiting restaurants for a hangout. In terms of Frequency of visit, it resulted to the fact that younger groups (ages 15-25) tend to visit restaurants occasionally compared to senior age groups (31-40+). In terms of average spending, it resulted to the fact that ages 21-40+ spends around BDT 1000-5000 per month and for ages 15-20 spend less than BDT 1000-5000. In conclusion, this research showed that the demographic profile such as gender and age vary based on the elements given. Based on this study, the researchers can input the importance of Gender and Age as a demographic factor to identify the correlation of K-Drama to K-Restaurants uprising mainly because of its trend. It is because of this trend of K-Drama, we can identify which age groups are significantly close to the topic and what gender is most influenced by the topic. Another demographic profile used is the occupation which determines the fact of where the respondents come from and how much are they earning. This will be considered.

2.2 Korean ‘Hallyu’ Uprising

According to Zakaria & Rahim (2020) “Korean wave or also known as ‘Hallyu’ in the Chinese language, symbolizes the global acceptance of the Korean cultural industries. It can be seen in the Malaysians’ youth following trends where it gradually influenced the lifestyle choices of food, cosmetics entertainment, and technology from the influence of Korean products. Growing demand for Korean food leads to an easing number of Korean food establishments in Malaysia” With that stated, it is noticed that Korean products are not only popular in Malaysia but in overall Asia such as the Philippines.

Because of technology today, easy access to watching K-drama led to the increase in demand for more shows to appear and better access to them. You may now see them mostly on Netflix these days. Because of these Korean shows being watched, the influence within those shows led to the hunger of achieving them for the viewers' own experience and thus led to demand for Korean restaurants within Malaysia. The scope of Zakaria & Rahim's research may be about the certification of halal food within Korean food businesses, but it also points out how technology was utilized and has a major contribution to the need/want of Korean products. It also states in their research that there was an age range of 21-30 that follows Malaysia Korean pop Fans (MKF) therefore age will be considered in the demographic profile.

2.3 Korean Cuisine as inspiration for Local Businesses

A study conducted by Otmazgin and Lyan (2019) about how Hallyu fans explore new business and social opportunities inspired by their fandom. In one interview from their research, Noga, an Israeli K-drama fan since 2007, started a Korean Food Business and then went to learn more about Korean Cuisine after seeing a Facebook advertisement looking for a chef to cook for a team of Korean engineers in a city in Israel. She then opened a small Korean food catering business, initiated Korean food workshops, and participated in Food Fairs. Her journey, together with other Hallyu fans, shows that their passion and motive drive them to promote Hallyu and Korean Cuisine Culture in their hometown. By adapting Korean Cuisine to their Local Cuisine which focuses on Kosher Foods because of their religion, Noga's skills could attract more audiences, especially religious Hallyu fans. The clients of these entrepreneurs are the Hallyu Fans themselves, but there will also be a second wave of consumers who would want to try Korean Foods. Otmazgin and Lyan's paper about Hallyu entrepreneurship shows how entrepreneurs can be influenced or inspired by Korean Cuisine when it comes to opening Local Businesses.

2.4 Impact of Hallyu in the Purchasing Intention of Filipinos

The study by Malabanan et al. (2022) shows that the Korean wave or "Hallyu" has a significant role in Filipinos' purchasing intentions for Korean products. The study was conducted in Metro Manila, Philippines and they found out that the Image and Popularity of Korean Culture scored the highest out of all the purchasing factors tested. Product placements on different Korean movies and series also received a high score following the factor of popularity while Advertisements of Popular Korean Personalities scored the same. These results meant that the popularity of Hallyu significantly impacted why Filipinos continue to support Korean Products and without these factors, Korean products will not be as popular today.

2.5 Korean Cuisine Worldwide Popularity

According to Nina Jobst (2022) Korean Cuisine has continued to gain worldwide popularity since early 2010, and 30% of 8500 respondents survey on Korean culture content in 2021, stated that Korean food was extremely popular in their country. This survey was conducted in the following countries: China, Japan, Taiwan, Thailand, Indonesia, Malaysia, India, Australia, Vietnam, United States, Brazil, Argentina, France, United Kingdom, Russia, Turkey, UAE, and South Africa. According to Kelly Beaton "Korean Cuisines has its moments in 2021, and all indications suggest, interest in Korean cuisine spiked nearly 90% in the 12 months leading up to January 2022"

2.6 Factors for decision-making Purchases

According to Yuan-Yuan Liu and Ha-kyun Kim in their study, they have identified certain factors to consider in terms of Chinese viewers watching Korean drama for motivation to buying Korean Cosmetics. These factors are Cultural Curiosity, Drama Attractiveness, Cultural Similarity, Relationship factor and Viewing Habit which all direct towards Korean Attractiveness and thus leading viewers to buy their products. Cultural curiosity "is the question related to the facilities where people want to know Korean Culture." Then we have 'Drama Attractiveness' referring to how do the viewers see the drama based on their liking, their "Viewing motive." After that we have Cultural Similarity wherein it states that Korea and China have similar traits in terms of the Drama show. Next, 'Relationship factor,' refers to the "desire to visit and live in Korea." Lastly, we have 'Viewing Habit' where it refers to the habit of viewing such content. The result led to a positive outcome where "Korea has a direct influence on the intention of purchase of Korean cosmetics among Chinese viewers who use Korean drama."

Based on these factors, we slowly understand and realize that Korean drama has a strong bond with customers around the world. The researchers may utilize these factors and understand how the customers think in today's time and age. What is most important to them, what truly motivates them into allowing themselves to be motivated to lead to such actions, is also known as their purchasing decision. "Often Consumers buy a product for reasons for excitement or desired emotions" (Sumarwan, 2011)

3. METHODOLOGY

This part discusses how the researchers will gather data in this study. This part shows the Design of the research, where it will be conducted, the participants of the study, and how the data will be treated.

Research Design

This study is Correlational Research Design which is a type of Quantitative Research since the researchers are aiming to know the effectiveness of the motivational factors to K-drama viewers to the rise of Korean Restaurants in Cavite using statistical data. Unlike Qualitative research design, the process of quantitative research is collecting and analyzing numerical data to find the average and patterns of variables, make predictions, test correlations, and generalize results of larger populations (Bhandari, 2022).

Research Locale

The study aims to know if there is any motivation between the K-drama viewers to the Rise of Korean Restaurants in Cavite. This study will be conducted at De La Salle University - Dasmariñas, but the researchers will fully utilize the online platform. The reason behind choosing Dasmariñas compared to other parts of Cavite since it is out of convenience for the researchers to detail upon.

Participants of the Study and Research Sampling

The Researchers chose students who are currently enrolled at De La Salle University-Dasmariñas taking up BS in Entrepreneurship with Specialization Track in Food Entrepreneurship in the Academic Year 2024-2025 as participants who also have watched Korean Dramas and had experience eating any Korean-related Foods. The sample size was determined by using Purposive Sampling Technique. The estimated sample size is 100-150 since the researchers are to choose voluntary participants that can match their preferred requirements.

Research Instrument & Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers will use a 5-point Likert scale and open-ended question survey questionnaire to gather data. This questionnaire has been validated by the research professor. The researchers will use the Google forms to conveniently collect data from their respondents. It will then be posted on their own social media platforms to look for respondents. The online questionnaire will be open for a month or until they have reached their target number of responses.

Data Treatment and Analysis

The researchers will use various data treatments to determine and analyze results. The Data will be treated differently according to each Statement of the Problem:

SOP #1 – Frequency and Percentage

SOP #2 – Frequency and Percentage

SOP #3 – Weighted Mean

SOP #4 – Frequency and Percentage

SOP #5 – Correlation Coefficient

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